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Record Maintenance and Tracking on Management of Senior Secondary School in Sokoto State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated the influence of record maintenance and record tracking on effective management of senior secondary schools in Sokoto State, Nigeria. The study was guided by two research questions and their corresponding null hypotheses. The study adopted a descriptive survey design. The population of the study was 3,960, comprising of 290 principals, 580 vice principals, 2,220 teachers and 870 PTA officials in all the public secondary school in Sokoto State. A sample of 349 respondents was selected and a self- designed questionnaire titled "record maintenance and tracking on the Management of Secondary Schools in Sokoto State" (RMTMSS) was used for data collection. The instrument was validated and 0.91 was obtained as content validity index. The questionnaire was pilot-tested and internal consistency reliability of 0.92 was obtained. Mean and Standard Deviation was used to answer the research questions, while chi-square was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that both record maintenance and tracking have significant impact on the management of Secondary Schools in Sokoto State, Nigeria. It was thus concluded that record maintenance and tracking are essential tools that enhance effectiveness in the management of public secondary schools. It was therefore recommended that seminars and excursions should be organized by Government, Non-Governmental Organizations and Quality Assurance Department, so that Principals will improve their record maintenance as it highly improves their management. Department of Education should also provide adequate training for record tracking in public schools; this will helps to increase their managerial effectiveness of their schools.

Keywords: Record, Maintenance, Tracking, Management, Secondary-school.

INTRODUCTION

Record has been defined by UNESCO (2020) as a document proof of a transaction; it can also refer to any activity which falls within necessary activities. Records are regarded as information handed down or preserved (NTI, 2018). Records is a kind of books and files or other document containing information relating to what goes on and what types of properties are kept (Kajo, 2020). Ozoemelan, (2018) records are written information about the school that will enable the authority to take decision and assess the progress of the school. Record are official documents, book and files containing essential information of action and events which are kept and preserved in the school office for utilization and retrieval of information when needed, such record are kept by principals, teachers, counselors or administrative staff (Aleiyodeino, 2018) . Hence the propose of record management is

to ensure that accurate and proper record of students achievement and growth, information on the school activities and matters that promote efficiency and effectiveness of the school system are kept (Uduak, 2019). Records are categorized in to statutory and non statutory records (Shehu, 2020). Non statutory record voluntarily kept in schools because of their importance value in school management. Non statutory record which include visitors book, minutes book, official correspondence file, inventory book, school budget, staff movement book and among others (Olowole, 2019). According to Ozoemelam (2018), posited that records are imperative in school management since it can aid successful operation of school activities.

Anyanwu (2019), the maintenance of school records is the sole responsibility of the school administrator. The maintenance of school records involves all the activities that ensure they are in good conditions (E.g. admission register, time book, certificate) and kept in an orderly state. Record maintenance Ogomuebulum (2020) continued to discuss that it is recommended to check files regularly so as to ensure that they are in a good condition since it is dangerous for them to tear and wear.

Record tracking It is important to make a follow up in order to know when files or record are sent to users or customers, the system should be able to know when and where files or records are sent and when are to be returned, in sometimes there are cards which are designed for the purpose of controlling the flow of files efficiently when they are in use. (Nnenna ogbu ans Ndubusi, 2023). Record tracking is the component of a record management system that ensures that you can locate records when you need to use them. Accurate recording and knowledge of the where about of all paper records. We need record tracking to keep track of the records we hold so that they can be located and managed effectively, and so that we can respond to freedom of information or data protection requests within the statutory deadlines (Onwurah, 2018).

It is the responsibility of each business area or schools to develop and implement a records management system for the records it holds. Records tracking are a vital part of that records management system. This might be implemented by the nominated practitioner for specific area concerned. Individual staff is the responsible for complying with any system which is set up and the records management section is available to provide advice about introducing and operating a records tracking system (Uduak, 2019).

Statement of the problems

With respect to the significance of record maintenance and tracking in schools for the achievement of the aim of school creation, researcher observed that these records were not adequately managed by the school administrators. Despite the main purpose of record keeping in the school system, the management of records in secondary schools in Nigeria still left much to be desired for effective administration. This suggests that school record planning and storage management practice in Nigeria has a number of issues. Based on these facts, it is glaring that a problem exists and this is the concern of this study. In spite of government policies, laws, regulations and public service schemes, it requires that both public and private schools should keep the school records for both teachers and students, but there are still many schools which are not able to keep and manage school records hence may result to the lack of sensitive records. The failure of school management to provide some records to support teachers and other stakeholders for their employment claim and failure of students to get their sensitive records on time such as academic certificates, as well as continuous assessments records have raised some questions among the researchers whether the school managements keep school records, (Okeke, 2015). This research therefore seeks to examine the extent to which record maintenance and tracking influence effective management of public secondary schools in Sokoto State Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of this research work include the following:

- i. To examine the impact of record maintenance on the management of the senior secondary school in Sokoto State.
- ii. To determine the impact of record tracking on the management of senior secondary school in Sokoto State.

Research Questions

The study seeks to answer the following research questions:

1. Does record maintenance affect the Management of Senior Secondary School in Sokoto State?
2. Does record tracking affect the Management of Senior Secondary School in Sokoto State?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses are tested at 0.5 level of significance:

H01: Record maintenance has no significant impact on the Management of Senior Secondary School in Sokoto State.

H02: Record tracking has no significant impact on the Management of Senior Secondary School in Sokoto State.

Literature review

Record maintenance and tracking have a great influence on school management. This suggests the planning and arrangement of records and files into different groups basing on their subjects so as to make sure that all records are logically maintenances. Record maintenance and school management to Anyanwu (2019), the maintenance of school records is the sole responsibility of the school administrator. Record tracking is the component of a record management system that ensures that you can locate records when you need to use them. Accurate recording and knowledge of the where about of all paper records (Ogomuebulum, 2020).

Researchers have carried out various studies to examine different variables of records for instance Odeniyi and Adeyanju, (2020) carried out a study with the purpose of assessment of school record management in secondary schools in federal capital territory Abuja. The descriptive research design was used for this study. The population was drawn from ten (10) secondary school in federal capital territory Abuja. The instrument for data collection comprised questionnaire titled "Assessment of School Record Management in Secondary Schools in FCT Abuja" (ASRMSS). A sample size of eighty (80) respondents from schools was used. Simple percentage was adopted in analyzing the research question while chi-square was adopted in analyzing the hypotheses. Research finding revealed that various school records that are currently kept in secondary school include; admission and withdrawal register, logbook, attendance register, school time table, diary, visitors' book, exam records, time movement book and a host of others. This is in line with the view of Olubebe (2013), which highlights the kind of records kept in schools. The results also revealed that school records are not properly kept as most of the seemingly kept records are not properly and effectively kept. This is in agreement with the view of Chifwepa, (2014), which opined that poor record keeping can be linked to policy summersault. Results also unveiled some strategies for improving on school records management in schools which include: timely supply of relevant school records, making funds available for record keeping purpose, training of personnel who keep records on a daily basis in school and finally providing proper back-up device for school records. This is equally in tandem with the assertion of (Olubebe, 2013). In his conclusion, results from the hypotheses revealed that school records are not properly kept; it also revealed that there is significant relationship between proper record management and efficiency of Secondary Schools.

Another study was conducted by Emeka and Rophina (2021), on the Records Management and Administration of Secondary Schools in Onuimo Local Government area of Imo State, Nigeria. The population of the study consisted of ninety-four (94) Business Educators in forty-eight (48) Senior and Junior Secondary Schools in Onuimo Local Government Area, Imo State. There was no sampling since the population was considered manageable. Two research instruments titled "Schools' Onuimo records management" and Achievement of smooth administration in Secondary Schools" in Onuimo Local Government Area were used in collecting responses from respondents. Mean and standard deviation was used in analyzing the data collected with 2.5 considered as decision point. Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) was used in testing the null hypotheses at $P > 0.05$ level of significance. The study showed that keeping and maintaining students' admission and attendance registers by the administration of Secondary Schools to a high extent contributed to smooth administration in the secondary schools in Onuimo Local Government Area. Administration cannot run smoothly without records. It became imperative for such records as admission register to be kept by schools to ensure accurate and proper information of students and determine the status of every

student in the school. It also assists the administration in monitoring students' participation in classroom and other activities of the school, students' bio-data and for effective planning and budgeting. The study further revealed that examination records, continuous assessment cards, among others contributed to the administration of Secondary Schools in Onuimo Local Government Area. Examination records, continuous assessment cards, among others to a high extent enhanced the administration of secondary schools in Onuimo Local Government Area. These records allow the administration to keep and maintain students' achievement records, track students' participation in classroom activities and check teachers' punctuality to classes. Examination Records shows students' performances in both internal and external examinations and future references are made with easy and without encumbrances. The study also revealed that school time table influenced the administration of secondary schools. Keeping and maintaining records help administration to keep track of teachers' teaching period and attendance to their teaching and learning activities, help to assess teachers' and students' performances in classroom activities. It also helps the administration in making sound administrative decision among others.

METHODOLOGY

A descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. According to Nwagwu (2007), descriptive survey design is one of the best designs for describing situation without manipulation. The population of the study comprised of 3,960 subjects which are made up of all the 290 principals, 580 vice principals, 2,220 teachers and 870 PTA officials of all the 290 public senior secondary school in Sokoto State. The researcher first determined 349 as the sample size of the population as guided by Research Advisor (2006). The instrument used for data collection was questionnaire titled ‘influence of record maintenance and record tracking in the management of senior secondary School in Sokoto’ (IRMTMSS). The questionnaire consisted mainly of close-ended structures which required the respondents to tick their best option and structured on three-point scale i.e. A= Agreed, D= Disagreed and C= UD Undecided. Descriptive statistics of frequency counts, percentages, mean and standard deviation were used to answer research questions, while inferential statistics chi-square were used to test the research hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

Research Questions one: *Does record maintenance affect the Management of Senior Secondary Schools in Sokoto State?*

Table 1: Extent of record maintenance effect on management of secondary schools

S/n	Variable	N	Rate%	Mean	SD	Remark
1	Record maintenance	344	90.00%	2.708	.36159	Record maintenance affects the management of secondary school
2	Management of secondary school	344	88.55%	2.656	.08273	‘

Source- Field Survey (2024)

The presented data in table 1 shows that record maintenance influence on the management of secondary schools. The result revealed that record maintenance was at rated 90.00% with number of participants n= 344, mean scored of 2.708 and Standard Deviation of 0.36159, indicating record maintenance has affects the management of Secondary Schools in Sokoto state, Nigeria. While management of secondary schools was at rated 88.55% with number of participants n= 344, mean scored of 2.656 and Standard Deviation of 0.08273, indicating the presence of management of secondary schools in Sokoto state, Nigeria. Thus, the record maintenance was rated higher than the management of secondary schools in Sokoto State, Nigeria. Record maintenance mean scored (2.708)

>management of secondary schools mean scored (2.656).Therefore, record maintenance has a highly affects the management of secondary schools in Sokoto State.

Research Questions two: Does record tracking affect the Management of Senior Secondary Schools in Sokoto State?

Table 2: Extent of record tracking effect on management of secondary schools

S/n	Variable	N	Rate%	Mean	SD	Remark
1	Record tracking	344	95.66%	2.873	.27332	Record tracking affects the management of secondary school
2	Management of secondary school	344	88.55%	2.656	.08273	

Source- Field Survey (2024)

The presented data in table 2 shows that record tracking affects the management of secondary schools. The result revealed that record tracking was at rated 95.66% with number of participants n= 344, mean scored of 2.873 and Standard Deviation of 0.27332, indicating record tracking has affects the management of Secondary Schools in Sokoto state, Nigeria. While management of secondary schools was at rated 88.55%with number of participants n= 344, mean scored of 2.656 and Standard Deviation of 0.08273, indicating the presence of management of secondary schools in Sokoto State, Nigeria. However, record tracking was rated higher than the management of secondary schools in Sokoto State, Nigeria. This is because, record tracking mean scored (2.873) >management of secondary schools mean scored (2.656).Therefore, record tracking greatly affects the management of secondary schools in Sokoto State.

H01: Record maintenance has no significant impact on the Management of Senior Secondary Schools in Sokoto State.

Table 3: Impact of Record maintenance on the Management of Secondary School

S/n	Variables	N	Mean	SD	DF	Chi-square	P-value	Decision
1	Record maintenance	344	2.708	.36159	343	234.149a		Ho1 Rejected
2	Management of Secondary school	344	2.656	.08273			.000	

Alpha level = 0.05

Table 3, reveals the number of participants (n) = 344, and a Chi-Square value = 234.149^aand P-value of .000. Testing the hypothesis at alpha level = 0.05. The P-value is less than alpha value, .000 < 0.05. Hence the null hypothesis which states that record maintenance has no significant impact on the management of senior secondary school in Sokoto State is hereby rejected. Therefore, there is significant impact of record maintenance on the management of secondary school. This means that the record maintenance enhance the management of secondary school in Sokoto State, Nigeria. By implication, it means that record maintenance leads to the effective management of secondary schools in Sokoto State, Nigeria.

H02: Record tracking has no significant impact on the Management of Senior Secondary school in Sokoto State.

Table 4: Impact of Record tracking on the Management of Secondary School

S/n	Variables	N	Mean	SD	DF	Chi-square	P-value	Decision
1	Record tracking	344	2.873	.27332		455.158a		
					343			Ho2 Rejected
2	Management of Secondary school	344	2.656	.08273			.000	

Alpha level = 0.05

Table 4, reveals the number of participants (n) = 344, and a Chi-Square value = 455.158^aand P-value of .000. Testing the hypothesis at alpha level = 0.05. The P-value is less than alpha value, .000 < 0.05. Hence the null hypothesis which states that record tracking has no significant impact on the management of senior secondary schools in Sokoto State is hereby rejected. Therefore, there is significant impact of record tracking on the management of secondary school. This means that the Record tracking enhance the management of secondary school in Sokoto State, Nigeria. By implication, it means that Record tracking leads to effective management of secondary schools in Sokoto State, Nigeria.

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

Findings from the first research question suggests that the extent to which the record maintenance on the Management of Secondary Schools in Sokoto State, Nigeria. The present finding is in consonance with the work of Omoha (2013) who reported that ideal administrative practices by administrators could ensure effective and efficient school record keeping management. Another study was conducted by Nnenna, Ogbu and Ndubuisi (2023) revealed that the principals were in agreement that most of the statutory records were adequately maintained with the exception of few records like; on the spot assessment record, weekly scheme of work, health record book, cash account book and copies of national policy on Education. The present finding is also not in agreement with the research finding of Idoko (2005) which showed that school record management will continue to suffer neglect and misappropriation unless school administrators employ desirable strategies for improving on school records keeping. This finding was not in line with Kachallah (2014) who submitted that a reasonable percentage of statutory records were not properly maintained in senior secondary schools in southern Yobe State.

However the second hypothesis showed that there is significant impact of record tracking on the Management of Secondary School in Sokoto State, Nigeria. The finding support the finding of Eno, (2018) stated that financial records deal with the management of schools' money. These records show the total amount the school has (income) and how much has been expended (expenditure) for the development of the school. If these records are properly kept, it saves the school administrator from unnecessary victimization or mismanagement of funds. Another study was conducted by Emeka and Rophina (2021), study showed that keeping and maintaining students' admission and attendance registers by the administration of Secondary Schools to a high extent contributed to smooth administration in the secondary schools in Onuimo Local Government Area. Ladoba and Kayode (2021) findings reveal that management practice variables when joined together significantly have relationship with record keeping thus enhancing effective secondary schools' administration in Nigeria. This report is not in agreement with that of Uzoho (2006) who submitted that there is a slight difference between the opinion of male and female secondary school principals on the administrative procedures that characterize the keeping of records in secondary schools in Umuahia education zone.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study it was concluded that record maintenance and tracking are essential for effective school management as they have significant positive effect towards that. Therefore all hands must be on deck to ensure proper maintenance and tracking of records for effective management to be met in all the secondary educational systems in the State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusions from this study the researcher recommends that:

1. Seminars and excursions should be organized by Government, Non-Governmental Organizations and Quality Assurance Department, so that Principals will improve their record maintenance as it highly improves their management.
2. Department of Education should provide adequate training for record tracking of secondary school's management. This will help to increase their managerial effectiveness of their schools.

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